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SLAG VALORISATION SYMPOSIUM

TACKLING FUTURE CRITICAL CHALLENGES

18-20 April 2023

Mechelen, Belgium

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SCREENING STRATEGY FOR Fe-RICH SLAG-BASED MORTARS

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Introduction

Fe-rich slags from non-ferrous metallurgical industries have been explored as supplementary cementitious materials (SCM)¹ and alkali-activated materials (AAM)². The use of such slags in construction has the potential to lower the carbon footprint of mortar/concrete through the replacement of high-impact binders like Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC). It also provides a sustainable template for using a residue generated at a rate of 30-40 Mt per annum³. In this paper, an attempt has been made to develop a model predicting early-age compressive strength⁴ of Fe-rich slag-based mortars from dynamic elastic modulus measurements (measured by ultrasound test) and porosity. Since non-destructive tests like ultrasound measurement involve time-efficient data collection, the current study is expected to aid in fast screening of Fe-rich slags as SCMs and AAM precursors. Similar work has already been carried out by Lootens et al.⁵ for cement-based pastes and concrete, while Lafhaj et al.⁶ and Chen et al.⁷ explain the effect of porosity on the acoustic wave velocity and compressive strength, respectively. The current study builds on the insights provided by the aforementioned authors and aims to address the relationship among early-age compressive strength, early-age dynamic elastic modulus and porosity for Fe-rich slag-based mortars.

Materials and Methods

An amorphous, industrial Fe-rich slag (52 wt% FeO) with a Blaine fineness⁸ of 4400 cm²/g was used. Additionally, for the blended and hybrid mixtures, CEM I 52.5N from Holcim and limestone powder from Calcitec (99.3% purity) were used. The mortar specimens were made as per EN 196-1: 2016⁴; they were sealed until the time of testing (up to 72 h) and cured at 20°C and 90% relative humidity (for tests at 7 d and 28 d after mixing). Table 1 provides a summary of the mixtures studied with a standard sand-to-binder ratio of 1.5 in all cases.

Table 1: Features of the mixture designs in the study

Mixture type	Binder composition (wt%)	Liquid composition	Liquid-to-binder ratio
Hybrid mortar 1	slag-70, CEM I 52.5N-20, limestone-10	1M NaOH activator	0.5
Hybrid mortar 2	slag-70, CEM I 52.5N-20, limestone-10	1M NaOH activator	0.4
Blended mortar 1	slag-30, CEM I 52.5N-70	water	0.5
Blended mortar 2	slag-30, CEM I 52.5N-70	water	0.4
Cement mortar 1	CEM I 52.5N-100	water	0.5
Cement mortar 2	CEM I 52.5N-100	water	0.4
Inorganic Polymer	NFMS-100	SiO ₂ /Na ₂ O: 1.6; 65% water content	0.4

For each mixture, the flow diameter⁹, compressive strength⁴, dynamic elastic modulus¹⁰ and porosity¹¹ were measured. The compressive strength tests for each mixture were conducted at approximate intervals (in h) of 5 and 6 (subject to intact specimens), 12, 24, 36, 48, 60 and 72 (h) after mixing. Additionally, compressive strength tests were also conducted at 7 d and 28 d to report the strength activity indices (SAI) of the mixtures. SAI is the percentage of compressive strength of a mortar sample as compared to the same-age compressive strength of the CEM I 52.5N-based mortar sample. Ultrasound measurements were performed up to 72 h after mixing, while porosity data were recorded (24 hours oven drying and 24 hours water sinking) after 28 d of curing. Further, linear regression analysis was performed on the collected data points using JMP Pro 17.0.

Results and discussions

Table 2 shows the flow diameter and compressive strength values (7 d and 28 d) along with the corresponding SAI. Blended mortars (30% Fe-rich slag) with water-to-binder ratio 0.4 exhibit the maximum compressive strength and the minimum porosity as compared to Inorganic Polymers (100% Fe-rich slag) and hybrid mortars (70% Fe-rich slag). As far as flow diameter is concerned, blended mortars exhibit the highest flowability in both cases of liquid-to-binder ratios (0.4 and 0.5). A key advantage to use these data for regression modelling is that the dataset provides a wide range of compressive strength data ranging from 9.9 MPa to 70.3 MPa (for 28 d) with different binder systems. Figure 1 depicts the plot (as obtained from JMP Pro 17.0) between the actual and predicted values of $\log_e(\text{Compressive strength})$ from the regression model (up to 72 h after mixing).

Table 2: Flow diameter, compressive strength and SAI (7 d and 28 d) and porosity

Mixture type	Flow dia. (mm)	7 d comp. strength (MPa)	7 d SAI (%)	28 d comp. strength (MPa)	28 d SAI (%)	Porosity (%)
Hybrid mortar 1	171	11.6 ± 0.4	22	16.4 ± 0.3	25	19.69 ± 0.4
Hybrid mortar 2	112	6.6 ± 0.8	13	9.9 ± 0.2	15	15.74 ± 0.2
Blended mortar 1	195	30.7 ± 0.5	59	52.1 ± 0.8	79	13.12 ± 0.3
Blended mortar 2	118	39.4 ± 0	76	57.5 ± 0.3	88	10.24 ± 0.4
Cement mortar 1	181	51.9 ± 0.8	100	65.6 ± 0.1	100	9.79 ± 0.2
Cement mortar 2	106	58.9 ± 1.6	114	70.3 ± 2.1	107	7.33 ± 0.2
Inorganic Polymer	180	37.3 ± 1.8	72	42.7 ± 2.1	65	13.04 ± 0.3

Figure 1: $\log_e(\text{Compressive strength})$ - actual vs predicted data

Equation (1) has been determined through linear regression analysis using JMP Pro 17.0:

$$\log_e(\text{Compressive strength}) = -1.4 + 4.9*P + 0.1*E_d - 0.002*(E_d-28)^2 - 135*(P-0.12)^2 \quad (1)$$

where, P: Porosity, E_d : Dynamic Elastic Modulus.

The corresponding RMSE and R^2 values in the regression model are 0.43 and 0.92, respectively, showing that the model can reliably predict compressive strength of Fe-rich slag-based mortars up to 72 h of mixing from dynamic elastic modulus up to 72 h and porosity at 28 d.

Conclusions

The study explored the relationship among early-age compressive strength, early-age dynamic elastic modulus and porosity for Fe-rich slag-based mortars as a part of different binder systems through regression modelling. The model is yet to be validated with different Fe-rich slags and does not yet show promising results for late-age compressive strength. Nevertheless, results so far indicate that the ultrasound test along with the porosity test can be used as a screening strategy for Fe-rich slag-based mortars.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958307. The project website is <https://h2020harare.eu/>.

References

1. Hallet, V., De Belie, N., & Pontikes, Y. (2020). The impact of slag fineness on the reactivity of blended cements with high-volume non-ferrous metallurgy slag. *Construction and Building Materials*, 257, 119400.
2. Beersaerts, G., Ascensao, G., & Pontikes, Y. (2021). Modifying the pore size distribution in Fe-rich inorganic polymer mortars: An effective shrinkage mitigation strategy. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 141, 106330.
3. Snellings, R. (2016). Assessing, understanding and unlocking supplementary cementitious materials. *RILEM Technical Letters*, 1, 50-55
4. European Committee for Standardization. (2016). *Methods of Testing Cement—Part 1: Determination of Strength* (EN 196-1). Retrieved from <https://edu.mynbn.be/pdfMeta/RO/558316?l=E>.
5. Lootens, D., Schumacher, M., Liard, M., Jones, S. Z., Bentz, D. P., Ricci, S., & Meacci, V. (2020). Continuous strength measurements of cement pastes and concretes by the ultrasonic wave reflection method. *Construction and Building Materials*, 242, 117902.
6. Lafhaj, Z., Goueygou, M., Djerbi, A., & Kaczmarek, M. (2006). Correlation between porosity, permeability and ultrasonic parameters of mortar with variable water/cement ratio and water content. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 36(4), 625-633.
7. Chen, X., Wu, S., & Zhou, J. (2013). Influence of porosity on compressive and tensile strength of cement mortar. *Construction and Building Materials*, 40, 869-874.
8. European Committee for Standardization. (2018). *Methods of Testing Cement—Part 6: Determination Of Fineness* (EN 196-6). Retrieved from <https://edu.mynbn.be/pdfMeta/RO/575635?l=E>
9. European Committee for Standardization . (2004).. *Methods of Test for Mortar for Masonry—Part 3: Determination of Consistence of Fresh Mortar (by Flow Table)* (EN 1015-3) . Retrieved from <https://edu.mynbn.be/pdfMeta/RO/165395?l=E> .
10. Beersaerts, G., Pontikes, Y., & Kriskova, L. (2021). *The Rheological and Shrinkage Behaviour of Fe-rich Slag-based Binders*.
11. European Committee for Standardization . 2011). *Methods of test for masonry units. Determination of water absorption of clay and calcium silicate masonry units by cold water absorption* (EN 772-21). Retrieved from <https://edu.mynbn.be/pdfMeta/RO/400613?l=E>.